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THE IMPACT OF SERVICE QUALITY ON TOURIST STISFACTION IN GUDDAPUR TOURIST CENTRE

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ABSTRACT

A tourist can be defined as a person who travels for pleasure/fun. Tourism is travelling for purely recreational or leisure purposes or the provision of services to support this leisure travel. Tourism is one of the largest service industries in India with a contribution of 6.23% to the national GDP and 8.78% to total employment in India. Tourists always visit a particular place in search of pleasure. Sometimes this motive is supplemented by other motives like business, education, religious, medical, friends and relatives etc. As like hotels, transport the tourism is fastest growing industries. Guddapur is selected for to analysis of tourist behavior satisfaction using various facilities. Tourist satisfaction assessment regarding a certain destination depends on attractiveness and specific tourist activity. This helps in making changes and modification in tourist programs and facilities of any destination. It is a duty of residents and tourist to behave in such a way that destination can become well known and popular. Culture provides a strong motivation for tourism

and the relation between culture and tourism. The Guddapur tourist center is selected for the analysis of tourism attractions and tourist satisfactions. For these, 300 tourist are selected during the whole one (2013) year. They selected on the basis of spot visiting persons in every month of New moon Day in year of 2013.

Keywords: motivation, satisfaction Index, culture, Dasoh

Introduction:

Tourism is temporary movement of people at a place outside their normal place of work or residence. Tourist always visits a particular place in search of pleasure. Tourism satisfaction depends upon the factors like accommodation, food, transport, behavioral of people, natural scenery, and other Administration etc. tourist satisfaction concerned with the attributes of behavior itself. In tourism different types of people connect each other. Such as tourists, travel agents, residents, enterprisers and administrators. It is quite necessary to keep co-ordination between them. This relationship depends on the behavior of these people and facilities provided at a reasonable rate which helps for increasing the level of satisfaction.

Shri Danamma devi is nobody, but the holy goddess mother Parvati, during 12th century, Once in the heaven god Parameshwar and mother Parvati have conversation about to make improvement of dharm(hindu religion) on earth god Parameshwar ordered to Parvati, to take birth on earth and have to do the work. Parvati humbly told that, without you I can't go to the earth, then both husband and wife have decided to take birth on earth to do the "Dharm Jagrati" awareness about religion. Mother goddess Parvati took birth on earth in small village called Unarani situated in Jath taluka, district Sangli (Maharashtra State) there lived a devotee couple Anantraya and Sirasamma the couple very worried as they had no children for the purpose of issue they solemnly prayed the lord "Veera Mallayya", the Lord Veermallayya pleased and accepted prayer by the couple and ordered to mother Parvati to take birth at said couple, Hence Parvati Ma took birth and the Lord Shiva took birth at Sourashtra and named as Somanath.

According to the religious procedure the female baby named as "Lingamma". Lingamma by the child hood itself she learnt the "Astanga" Ling, jangam, Bhasma (vibhuti), Rudrakshi, Padodaka, Theerth, Prasad and the Guru". During the due- course she grown up the father and mother were thinking about the marriage of "Lingamma". The matter solved by Lingamma's "Guru" as the father lord shiva look birth and named as Somanath, after renamed "Someshwar" marriage procedure done in presence of "KING". At that time it look in silent hilly place near by Guddapur and called as "Sanga Theerth". After some days both the Lingamma and Someshwar are decided to go for canvassing the Hindhu Religion, parents of Lingamma worried about the matter.

During the Dharm Sanchar, Lingamma, sacrificed for "Veerashaiv Dharma" and gave the concept about it to common people, and also she provided the knowledge about the "Ashtavaran" and Lingamma has done several miracles too during the Dharma Sanchar. During course they went to Solapur Sidharameshwar and Shrishail Mallikarjun and many other holy places. During the wondering they went to Lord Basavanna's "Anubhava Mantap" and there nearby in the Banana Field, when sited for Ling Poojan and forget herself in the Pooja. There even the Banana, Coconut and Flower trees were bent in respect and saluted. The pilgrims looked astonishingly and message from one to other spread speedily and it was heard by Lord Basavanna. Lingamma over all this factor showed the importance of Prasad and done some miracles of Prasad, looking into the matter Lord Basavanna invited the Lingamma to Anubhav Mantap and renamed Lingamma as "Anna Daneshwari". During the course of Dharma Sanchar they went everywhere and at last in the year 1128 Danamma mingled soulfully in the stone idol, which is already ided by her father at Guddapur.

Objectives:

Some specific objectives of the study are as follows-

1. To behavior of tourist at Guddapur tourist center in Sangli district.
2. To asses the satisfaction of tourist who visits of Guddapur.
3. To find out the miss management and facility provided for tourist in Guddapur.

Study Area:

Guddapur is a Village in Jath Taluka in Sangli District of Maharashtra State,

India. It belongs to Desh or Paschim Maharashtra region. It belongs to Pune Division. It is located 107 km towards East from District head quarters Sangli. 23 km from Jath. 403 km from State capital Mumbai. Asangi (3 km), Sordi (5 km), Madgyal (5 km), Daribidachi (7 km), Gondhalewadi (7 km) are the nearby Villages to Guddapur. Guddapur is surrounded by Bijapur Taluka towards East, Sangola Taluka towards North, Mangalwedha Taluka towards North, Athni Taluka towards South. Guddapur tourist centre is famous for the Shri Danamma devi temple which is located at 1704'3.5" North latitude and 75023'43.12" East longitude.

Map No.1 Location Map of Guddapur Tourist Center

Database and Methodology:

This study is completely based on field work collected questionnaires. Here attempt had been made to assess the level of satisfaction of tourist by considering their views about facilities provided at the destination. With the help of questionnaires researcher interviewed 300 tourist in Guddapur and asked their opinion about the facilities in term of excellent, good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory through questionnaires. These views were then converted into numerical values such as 8 to 10 for excellent, 6 to 7 for good, 4 to 5 for satisfactory and 1 to 3 for unsatisfactory.

The following formula is used for calculating satisfaction Index, Relative importance index and ultimate satisfaction index.

$$Sti = \frac{\sum Mi \times Ni}{N}$$

Where,

Sti = satisfaction index for I factor

Mi = Numerical values for particular level of satisfaction for I factor

Ni = number of respondents deriving the particular level of Satisfaction for the I factor.

N = Total number of respondents for that factor for all level of Satisfaction

Ultimate satisfaction index is the combined product of satisfaction index and tourist relative importance based the weighted satisfaction index. It was computed for Guddapur tourist center. The formula for obtaining satisfaction index is given as below

$$USI = \frac{\sum Si \times Ri}{\sum Si}$$

Where,

USI = Ultimate satisfaction index

Si = satisfaction Index

Ri = Relative Importance

By applying above formula we have calculated the satisfactory index, relative index and ultimate satisfactory index of this study. By considering the Accommodation, co-operative of local people, Destination queue, Dasoh, Management, Parking facilities, Personal safety, Primary Basic facilities, Spot guidance and Transport etc. tourist were

express their satisfaction index in the points(out of 10) and the classification was done on the basis of selected numerical values.

Profile of Tourist Behavior Guddapur Tourist Center:

The development of any tourist place is depending on the various factors. However here on attempt has made to assess the level of satisfaction by adopting satisfaction index method.

Table No.1: Factor wise level of Satisfaction

Sr. No.	Factor	Distribution of Respondents				Total
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Un-satisfactory	
1	Accommodation	240	32	19	09	300
2	Co-operative of Local people	132	89	46	33	300
3	Darshan Queue facility	271	19	08	02	300
4	Dasoh	178	108	16	05	300
5	Management	82	93	87	38	300
6	Parking Facility	54	86	71	89	300
7	Personal safety	119	93	51	37	300
8	Primary Basic Facilities	91	72	69	68	300
9	Spot guidance	32	38	49	181	300
10	Transport	83	95	78	44	300
	Total	1282	718	494	506	3000
	Average	128.2	71.8	49.4	50.3	300
	Percentage	42.73	23.93	16.47	16.87	

Source: Field work

Table No. 1 reveals the level of satisfaction at Guddapur tourist center. The tourist has responded to the various factors in ranking namely excellent, good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory. For these 10 factors average of each category calculated which gives the view of tourist about them facilities at Guddapur. Category wise satisfaction reveals that the facilities provided are excellent 42.73%, good 23.93%, satisfactory 16.47 and unsatisfactory 16.87%.

Table No.2: Factor wise Average of Satisfaction (Ni)

Sr. No.	Factor	Distribution of Respondents			
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Un-satisfactory
1	Accommodation	9.14	6.59	4.58	2.33
2	Co-operative of Local people	8.78	6.44	4.59	2.48
3	Darshan Queue facility	9.36	6.48	4.62	3.00
4	Dasoh	9.60	6.62	4.69	2.60
5	Management	9.13	6.62	4.49	2.29
6	Parking Facility	9.02	6.62	4.66	2.35
7	Personal safety	9.48	6.50	4.63	2.35
8	Primary Basic Facilities	9.08	6.61	4.54	2.12
9	Spot guidance	9.09	6.55	4.65	2.32
10	Transport	9.10	6.49	4.52	2.16

Source: compiled by Researcher

The tourist opinion about the factors shows in table no.2 and it is calculated average namely 8 to 10 for excellent, 6 to 7 for good, 4 to 5 to satisfactory and 1 to 3 for unsatisfied. These numerical value are used to calculate satisfaction score and satisfaction index. It was noted that response given most excellent was mentioned to Dasoh factor (9.60) and the minimum is co-operative of local people (8.78). Under the unsatisfactory category the most unsatisfactory is Primary basic facilities followed by transport (2.16).

Table No.3 Ranking of factors and satisfaction at Guddapur tourist center

Sr. No.	Factor	Satisfaction Index	Rank
1	Accommodation	8.37	2
2	Co-operative of Local people	6.75	5
3	Darshan Queue facility	9.01	1
4	Dasoh	8.22	3
5	Management	6.14	5
6	Parking Facility	5.32	9
7	Personal safety	6.81	4
8	Primary Basic Facilities	5.86	8
9	Spot guidance	3.96	10
10	Transport	6.06	7

Source: Field work

Table No.3 shows ranking and satisfaction index for Darshan Queue facility (9.01) is high followed by accommodation (8.37). The minimum satisfaction index is spot guidance (3.96). This study also shows that satisfaction index having Dasoh on 3rd rank, Personal Safety on 4th rank and parking facility on 9th rank.

It is noticed that Guddapur tourist shows the preferences to Darshan Queue facility, Accommodation and Dasoh. On other hand less preferences was given to spot guidance, parking facility and primary basic facility in this tourist center.

Table No.4: Factor wise order of importance attached by tourist

Sr. No.	Factor	Order of importance				Total	Relative Respondents	Rank
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th			
1	Accommodation	28	32	176	64	300	5.20	8
2	Co-operative of Local people	46	58	93	103	300	5.39	7
3	Darshan Queue facility	13	47	83	157	300	4.30	9
4	Dasoh	21	19	33	227	300	3.62	10
5	Management	113	83	31	73	300	6.97	4
6	Parking Facility	72	89	78	61	300	6.43	5
7	Personal safety	96	28	103	73	300	6.22	6
8	Primary Basic Facilities	124	78	62	36	300	7.42	2
9	Spot guidance	89	98	62	36	300	7.01	3
10	Transport	142	93	47	18	300	7.99	1

Source: compiled by Researcher

Relative importance and the ranking factors shown in table No.4. In this table, 1st ranking identified for transport (7.99), 2nd is for Primary basic facility (7.42) and 3rd for spot guidance. Other hand the lowest means last rank is identified for Dasoh (3.62).

It is highlighted that the influencing factor are Transport, Primary basic facility and spot guidance.

$$USI = \frac{S_i \times R_i}{R_i} = 6.40$$

It is noticed that transportation and accommodation has contributed maximum satisfaction index 48.42 and 43.52 respectively. Primary basic facility followed by third rank and it has contributed 43.48 ultimate satisfactions. On other hand spot guidance, Dasoh and parking facility ranks 10th, 9th and 8th respectively, with 27.76, 29.76 and 34.20 ultimate index.

Table No.: 5 Factor wise contribution of ultimate Index

Sr. No.	Factor	Guddapur tourist Center		SI × RI	Rank
		Satisfaction Index(SI)	Relative Importance(RI)		
1	Accommodation	8.37	5.20	43.52	2
2	Co-operative of Local people	6.75	5.39	36.38	7
3	Darshan Queue facility	9.01	4.30	38.74	6
4	Dasoh	8.22	3.62	29.76	9
5	Management	6.14	6.97	42.79	4
6	Parking Facility	5.35	6.43	34.20	8
7	Personal safety	6.81	6.22	42.36	5
8	Primary Basic Facilities	5.86	7.42	43.48	3
9	Spot guidance	3.96	7.01	27.76	10
10	Transport	6.06	7.99	48.42	1

Source: compiled by Researcher

Conclusion:

Guddapur tourist center is part of Sangli district in Jat tahsil. It can be summarized that the satisfaction of tourist shows rate of tourism development level at historical tourism and cultural tourism. Tourist satisfaction depends upon the factors like accommodation, food, transport, good communication, natural scenery, shopping facilities, co-operation of local people, behavioral of people etc. The results of Guddapur tourist center is mentioned as below.

Ultimate satisfaction index of Guddapur center is 6.40 out of 10 points.

There is 28 Nos single room facility in Guddapur tourist center.

There is 161 nos of attached room in this tourist center.

There is 2 Mangalkaryalaya in Guddapur.

One of good facility in Guddapur is Dasoh, which provides Prasad in 12:30pm to 3:00pm and 7:30pm to 10:00pm to every day to all tourists.

Lack of spot guidance in Guddapur tourist center.

There is problem of toilet facility.

Problem of good restaurants.

Scarcity of pure drinking water.

There is not sufficient entrainment facility.

Devastan Trust is continuously taking efforts to improve facilities for devotes and today we can experience the result by visiting Guddapur. Lot of things has been changed during last few years. Whatever we did is just become of Devi Dhaneshwararies blessing and devotes co-operation.

References

1. Agrawal S.K. & Raina A.K. (2004): "The essences of tourism development" Sarup and Sons, New Delhi.
2. Aparna Raj (2004): "Tourist Behavior-A psychological Perspective", Kanishka publisher Distributors, Ansari Road, Darya Gang, New Delhi.
3. Bae-Haeng Cho (1998): "Assessing Tourist Satisfaction-Tourist Recreation Research, Vol. No.23(I), Pp.47-54.
4. Batta K.L. (1989): "Problems and Prospects of Tourism" Printwell Publisher, Jaipur.
5. Chawla R. (2006): "Impact of Tourism" Sonali Publication, New Delhi.
6. J.P. Jagtap (2008): "A Geographical study of Tourism center in Solapur District." Unpublished Ph.D thesis, submitted to Solapur University Solapur.
7. Ligade D.N. & Todkari G.U. (2013): "An Assessment of Satisfaction level of Mangalwedha tourist center, Solapur district.-Maharstra Geographical Vol.1(II) Pp.52-58
8. Moutinho, L. (1987): "Consumer Behavior in Tourism: European Journal of Marketing" Vol.9 (spring), Pp.8-17
9. Ryan, A.M. (1996). "Research Tourist Satisfaction-Issues, Conceptual Problems". Routledge, Canada and New York.
10. Selvam, M: "Tourism Industry in India-A study of its growth and Development Needs" Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai.